

A COMPARISON OF FATIGUE DAMAGE DETECTION IN CARBON AND GLASS FIBRE EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIALS BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION

by J. HOLT and P. J. WORTHINGTON

*Central Electricity Research Laboratories
Materials Division
Kelvin Avenue - Leatherhead - Surrey U.K.*

Ring specimens of four fibre composite materials, two containing carbon (CFRP) fibres and two containing glass fibres (GFRP) have been monitored for acoustic emission (AE) during tension-tension fatigue cycling.

In CFRP continuous monitoring failed to provide warning of impending fatigue failure. The results are not consistent with the view that cessation of activity after initial shakedown guarantees stabilisation and safe operation.

In GFRP, if the activity is averaged over adequate periods, an underlying trend is revealed, short term deviations from which are attributed to the occurrence of a different damage process which determines final failure. It is shown that in the tests reported, the progressively increasing component of the activity can be related to the fatigue life. The distribution of events over the load cycle shows that a dominant part of this progressively increasing activity is associated with some stress independent process. Use of the appropriate part of the load cycle also offers the possibility of focussing on the events associated with the damage that leads to final failure.

INTRODUCTION

A number of potential applications exist for high specific strength fibre composite materials in rotating electrical machinery and other devices for energy conversion and storage. Such applications would require rigorous monitoring of the integrity of components subjected to long term thermal and mechanical fatigue loading. Acoustic emission (AE) monitoring is one possible method of doing this. Of particular interest, therefore, is the proposal [1] that in CFRP structures, if a sensitivity is used such that only fibre breakage is detected, then cessation of activity after shakedown is an indication of stabilisation and safe operation. In the case of GFRP, such stabilisation does not apparently occur [2] and other approaches such as the breakdown of the Kaiser Effect are of interest [3].

Many of the above applications for composite materials involve ring type structures and in this paper we describe the results obtained by AE monitoring small ring specimens of two types of CFRP and two types of GFRP.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ring specimens used were approximately 69.1mm in diameter, 12.7mm wide and 1.6mm thick and were prepared by filament winding with a special technique which eliminates voidage [4]. Four different types of fibre were used. Courtauld's E-HT/S and Toraya high modulus carbon fibres, and Silenka 'E' and 'R' glass fibres. The four composites all contained 55% by volume of fibre and the matrix was Ciba-Geigy epoxy MY750. The majority of the rings were hoop wound but some tests were performed on 70° angle wound rings fabricated with the E-HT/S fibre. The rings were fatigued in tension-tension loading using a sinusoidal load cycle with R=0.1 and a frequency of 1Hz for the majority of the tests, although lower frequencies and different load cycles were also used. Initial experiments were carried out using a split dee loading system but more recent tests have used hydraulic pressurisation. In the split dee arrangement, a Dunegan/Endevco resonant (140kHz) transducer was mounted directly on the ring, using an appropriately contoured "shoe" and silicone grease as a coupling medium. The electronic bandwidth was from 100-300kHz and the threshold 1 volt. Facilities were available for ringdown counting, event counting, energy and amplitude assessment. In the hydraulically pressurised system, a miniature transducer (Dunegan-Endevco type S1000BM) was immersed in hydraulic fluid filling the outer space of the pressurisation chamber; the face of the transducer was positioned about 5mm from the outer face of the ring. Measurements using a pulsed transducer source showed that the sensitivity of this arrangement was approximately 26dB less than that used in the split dee system.

RESULTS

(a) Fatigue of CFRP

Initial work was carried out using the split dee loading system and the E-HT/S fibre composites. Fatigue failures were obtained after a reasonable (up to 10⁶) number of cycles in angle wound rings but could not be obtained in hoop wound rings. In both cases, when monitored at a gain of 60dB, a sensitivity considered reasonable for detecting only fibre fracture [1], it was indeed observed that after an initial shakedown period, the system became quiet. However the fatigue failures which occurred in the angle rings did so after prolonged periods of such inactivity, without any warning of impending failure. An example is shown in Fig. 1. The results obtained in simultaneous monitoring at higher gains (80dB) merely showed continuing activity throughout the test with no significant trend indicative of impending failure.

Hoop wound rings fabricated from the E-HTS fibres exhibit flat S-N curves close to the lower limit of the scatter in the ultimate stress values. This made difficult to generate true fatigue failures in reasonable periods. Hoop wound rings made from the Toray fibres which became available later show S-N curves with measurable slope and true fatigue failures could consequently be produced in such rings. An example of

the final stage of such a failure is shown in Fig. 2. In this case, the gain used (96dB) was equivalent to approximately 70dB in the split dee system. The emission count rate rapidly decreased to a few counts per cycle and remained so until the final failure period. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the extent of any warning is at most a few percent of the fatigue life.

In the absence of long term warning of impending fatigue failure the details of the emission behaviour over the final failure cycles becomes more important. One possibility is the use of the breakdown of the Kaiser Effect. To this end measurements were made of the activity obtained at high gain (97dB) in the split dee system from rings failed over about 20 cycles by progressive increments in the maximum stress. Fig. 3 shows the results obtained on reloading rings where in both cases the previous maximum load happened to be close to 75% of the final failure load. Significant activity became detectable at ≈40% of the previous maximum load (≈30% of the failure load) in the hoop wound ring but only at 85% (≈60% of failure load) in the angle wound ring.

(b) Fatigue of GFRP

In the GFRP rings the emission activity was generally found to be far greater than that from CFRP. Also, in contrast to the inactivity of CFRP after shakedown, in GFRP, although there was a rapid decay from very high activity over the first few cycles, this was followed by a general trend of increasing activity, but with pronounced short-term fluctuations. By averaging over a sufficiently long period (500 cycles) it was found possible to reasonably approximate the underlying trend in these particular tests by

$$N = a(C C_f)^{1.5} \quad \dots (1)$$

where N is the emission count /500 cycles, C the number of cycles, C_f is the number of cycles to cause failure, and $a=1.10^{-7}$. Examples of results on E glass and R glass are shown respectively in Figs. 4 and 5. The high activity during shakedown over the first five cycles is not shown. The gains used (80dB) correspond to only 54dB in the split dee system where 60dB is considered sufficiently low to detect only fibre fracture in CFRP. In Figs. 4 and 5, the first significant deviations from Eq. (1), which occur at 60% and 70% respectively of the failure life, are interpreted as due to major new damage, the second such major deviation leading to final failure. The feature that such periods of enhanced activity are followed by less active ones, which do not indicate stabilisation occurs within what is, on the scale of Figs. 4 and 5, the final failure period. Fig. 6 shows the details of the activity recorded over the final 200 cycles of the test on the R glass specimen in Fig. 5, with again an absence of a progressive increase in activity towards failure.

The overall trend of increasing activity in GFRP is accompanied by an increase in the average signal amplitude measured over the whole range extending down to the background noise. Fig. 7 shows the amplitude distribution function obtained over two periods of the test on the R glass specimen shown in Fig. 5. For the period 100-1000 cycles the amplitude distribution is reasonably approximated by

$$N(V) = A V^{-m} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $N(V)dV$ is the number of signals with amplitudes in the range $V \rightarrow dV$, A is a constant and $m=3.9$. Although such a power law approximation does not hold over the whole spectrum obtained in the final stage of the test, the lower initial slope, $m=2.3$, and the development of the curvature, indicate a larger average signal amplitude [5].

Further information about the nature of the activity responsible for the underlying increasing emission rate may be obtained from an examination of the phase of the load cycle at which the emissions occur. For example, Fig. 8A shows the distribution over the load cycle of all those events $>100\mu V$ at the transducer, which occurred in the last 200 cycles of the test on the E glass specimen Fig. 4. The number of events in each load interval has been normalised by dividing by the time per cycle spent in that interval (sinusoidal loading). The distribution shown thus re-

presents the probability per unit time of an event at a given load. The general flatness of the distribution is thus indicative of large contribution to the activity by events which occur at random, independent of load. If the threshold is raised to 400 μ V the distribution develops a pronounced peak at 80-85% of the peak of the load swing Fig. 8B.

(c) Time dependent effects

The known time dependent properties of the matrices used in fibre reinforced materials means that consideration must also be given to frequency and waveform effects in fatigue monitoring. Although no systematic examination has yet been made, some idea of the likely effects can be obtained from the example in Fig. 9. This shows the results obtained by loading a hoop wound GFRP ring (E glass) in the split dee loading system using the "triangular waveform" shown in the insert to the figure. The decay of the activity over the early cycles would, on the basis of the previously described results, have been followed by a progressive increase. After the twelfth cycle, however, the load was increased to the peak value and held. The activity generated during the subsequent hold greatly exceeded that during the preceding cycles and was an appreciable fraction of that obtained on first loading. The time dependence of the activity generated during the hold at maximum load was logarithmic Fig. 10.

DISCUSSION

In the tests described, AE monitoring of fatigue loaded CFRP rings did not provide long term warning of impending fatigue failure. The cessation of activity when operating at a sensitivity considered sufficiently low to allow only fibre fracture to be detected [1] was not an indication of stabilisation and safe operation. Operation at higher gains merely resulted in activity throughout the tests with no indication of impending failure. It appears then that continuous monitoring of CFRP structures subject to fatigue will not provide a reliable method of assessing integrity. Attention must therefore be directed towards intermittent testing, such as breakdown of the Kaiser Effect at loads above the maximum fatigue load as a means of assessing the progress of fatigue damage. The results obtained on this effect show that careful consideration must be given to the exact winding configuration involved.

In GFRP, where prolonged absence of emission activity after shakedown does not occur, the results show some evidence for an underlying progressive build up in emission rate with superimposed periods of high activity tentatively associated with some different damage process which ultimately leads to failure. The results also indicate a possible means of analysing the underlying monotonic increase in activity and using it to predict fatigue life, although a more extensive programme is required to determine the generality of this approach. The observation, Fig. 8A, that even in the final stages of the test, the signals other than the very largest contain a large component generated at random independent of stress, suggests that the underlying trend of increasing activity is associated with some internal frictional process. In this connection it should be noted that since this activity randomly distributed with respect to stress increases by at least two orders of magnitude during tests conducted at constant stress amplitude, it is not due to some extraneous random noise source. The preferential occurrence of the very largest signals in the final failure stage at a particular stress value, Fig. 8B, offers the possibility of improved selection of the important damage events.

The measurements reported have been predominately at 1Hz with a sinusoidal load cycle. In many applications very different frequencies and load waveforms will be involved and investigations of the effects of the time dependent behaviour Figs. 9 and 10 are obviously a further requirement.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1 In CFRP, continuous AE monitoring does not provide warning of impending fatigue failure.

- 2 Cessation of activity at low sensitivity (or stable activity at higher sensitivity) do not necessarily indicate safe operation.
- 3 In GFRP long term averaging reveals an underlying progressive increase in activity during fatigue cycling, which offers the possibility of predicting fatigue life.
- 4 A large component of the increasing activity in GFRP is associated with some stress independent process.
- 5 Selection of the appropriate phase of the load cycle in GFRP permits isolation of other damage events which are associated with the actual failure process.

REFERENCES

- 1 BUNSELL, A.R., 1977, N.D.T. International, p. 21, February.
- 2 FUWA, M., BUNSELL, A.R., HARRIS, B., 1974, Proc. Conf., Composites: Standards and Design, I.P.C. Tech. Press, for N.P.L. pp 77-79.
- 3 POLLOCK, A.A., WADIN, J.R., 1977, National SAMPE Tech. Conf., 9, Fall, 1977, pp 519-560.
- 4 WORTHINGTON, P.J., 2nd International Conf. on Composite Materials, Toronto, 1978.
- 5 HOLT, J., GODDARD, D.J., 1979, Central Electricity Research Labs., Research Note, RD/L/Ni59/79.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was carried out at the Central Electricity Research Laboratories and is published by permission of the Central Electricity Generating Board.

Fig. 1. CFRP ring, E-HTS fibre, 70° angle wound, tested in split dee system, max. stress 450MPa., gain 60dB.

Fig. 2. CFRP ring, hoop wound, Toray fibre, tested in hydraulic pressurisation system, max. stress 700MPa., gain 96dB.

Fig. 3. CFRP rings, hoop and angle wound (70°), E-HTS fibre, cycled to progressively increased stress, behaviour shown is that after previous load in each case was 75% of the failure load.

Fig. 4. CFRP ring, E glass, hoop wound, tested hydraulically, max. stress, 750MPa., gain 80dB. (emission on first five cycles not shown).

Fig. 5. GFRP ring, R glass, hoop wound, tested hydraulically, max. stress 750MPa., 80dB. gain. (emission on first five cycles not shown.)

Fig. 6. Final 200 cycles of R glass ring (Fig. 5), gain 80dB.

Fig. 7. Amplitude distribution functions of R glass specimen (Fig. 5) taken over 100-1000 and 5560-7000 (failure) cycles.

Fig. 8. Distribution of events over load cycle final 500 cycles in test on E glass ring (Fig. 4): A - events with amplitudes $>100\mu\text{V}$ at transducer; B - events with amplitudes $>400\mu\text{V}$ at transducer.

Fig. 9. GFRP ring, hoop wound E glass, loaded with waveform shown inset, max. stress 400MPa., and held at max. stress after 13th loading; tested in split dee, 70dB gain. (failure stress 1000MPa)

Fig. 10. Time dependence of the activity recorded during the hold period of the test shown in Fig. 9.